

Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Pulses Cultivation in Yesagy Township

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Abstract

This research is an attempt to analyze the pulses cultivation in Yesagy Township. In carrying out this research, the primary and secondary data collected during the field survey is used and the pulses cultivation and production in Yesagy Township are separately analyzed using statistical methods. To examine the concentration of pulses sown acreage in Yesagy Township by village tract, the location quotient method adopted by (Dr. S. S. Bhatia) is used. The level of concentration classified into three classes namely high, medium and low: seven village tracts in high concentration of pulses, Yesagy Town Proper and 59 village tracts in medium concentration of pulses and five village tracts in low concentration of pulses. The trends of each pulses sown acreage and production during 15- year period from 2002-2003 to 2016-2017 are analyzed by regression lines. It is also necessary to expand the pulses sown acreage because pulse is an export crop and it gives more income for farmers. This research can provide to the development of agricultural sector in Yesagy Township.

Key words: location quotient method; level of concentration; Yesagy Township.

Introduction

Myanmar is an agricultural country therefore the nation's economy mainly depends on agriculture. Agriculture is a key sector of Myanmar's economy. After 1988, Myanmar adopted a market oriented economy and farmers were allowed freedom of choice on crop cultivation and production. Pulses crops such as chick pea, green gram, pigeon pea, cow pea, lablab bean, black gram, butter- bean, sultani, sultapya, soya –bean and other pulses are cultivated in Yesagy Township.

The main cultivated crops in Myanmar are cereals, oil seed crops, pulses, industrial crops and others. **Pulses** are defined in seventh edition of Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English as any of the seeds some plants that are eaten as food, such as peas and lentils. According to 2016-2017 data, of the total pulses cultivated acreage of about 118,083 acres in Pakokku District, about 75,758 acers or 13.06 percent is cultivated in Yesagy Township. Although the study area is located in Central Dry Zone of Myanmar, it practises in agriculture with dry crop cultivation. That is a main reason, why Yesagy Township is chosen as a study area in order to understand the distribution pattern of pulses cultivation.

Study Area

Yesagy Township is located in the Dry Zone of Central Myanmar's. It is situated in the Pakokku District, the northern part of Magway Region. It lies on the west bank of Ayeyarwady-Chindwin confluence. It falls between latitudes 21° 20' north and 21° 51' north and between longitudes 95° east and 95° 20' east. Although Yesagy Township is the smallest area within Pakokku District, net sown area has the third largest. Therefore, to get insight understanding the condition of pulses cultivation in the Yesagy Township, it is necessary to compare its physical factors, and amount of cultivation and production of pulses.

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Aim and Objectives

The main aim of this research is to know the role of pulses cultivation in Yesagy Township.

The objectives are

- to examine which pulses crop is the most important in Yesagy Township
- to evaluate the spatial pattern of pulses cultivation in Yesagy Township
- to analyse the temporal change of pulses cultivation in Yesagy Township
- to predict the future pulses cultivation in Yesagy Township

Materials and Method

Materials which are required for this research have been collected from various sources. Primary data are collected by making the personal interview and questionnaire design within the field trips. The secondary data are obtained from the respective offices. The collected data have been classified and processed, and then they are transformed to the forms of tables, figures and maps by applying the quantitative and qualitative methods.

Finally, geographical interpretations of the results have been done with the help of maps and figures.

Physical and non physical bases of Study Area

Yesagy is situated in the Pakokku District, the northern part of Magway Region. It lies on the west bank of Ayeyarwady-Chindwin confluence. It falls between latitudes 21° 20' north and 21° 51' north and between longitudes 95° east and 95° 20' east. The location of the study area is shown in (Map. 1). The total area of Yesagy Township is 385.73 square miles or 246,870 acres. Yesagy Township consists of Yesagy Town Proper with 8 wards and 81 village tracts with 245 villages. It has a compact shape. The townships adjoining to Yesagy Township are on the north by Salingyi and Chaung Oo Township, on the east by Myaung and Myingyan Township, on the south by Pakokku Township and on the west by Myaing Township.

As Yesagy Township lies on the plain of the river basin where the Chindwin joins with the Ayeyarwady, the relief feature is quite flat except the *Shinmataung* range. Ayeyarwady River is important not only for the transportation but also for the irrigation of the study area. During the 30-year period from 1988 to 2017, the average mean temperature 81.66°F, the average maximum temperature and average minimum temperature of Yesagy was 96.37°F and 67.07°F respectively. The hottest month is May with the average mean temperature of 88.67°F and the coldest month is January with the average mean temperature of 70.28°F. Thus, the range of temperature is 18.39°F. In this period, the average annual rainfall of Yesagy is 24.46 inches. According to Koppen's Classification of Climate, Yesagy has Tropical Steppe Climate (BSh). The distribution of soil types are found in Yesagy Township such as: Alluvial Soils, Meadow Alluvial Soils, Cinnamon Alluvial Soils, Red Brown Savanna Soils Eroded Red Brown Savanna Soils and Gravelly Red Brown Savanna Soils. Dry forests are found within Yesagy Township.

According to table (1), the proportion of urban population is increasing while the proportion of rural population is declining in Yesagy Township during 43-year period from 1973 to 2017. According to 2017 population data, Yesagy Township has a total population of 242,922 persons. Out of this total number of population, the urban population is 23,231 persons with the 9.56 percent and the rural population is 219,691 persons with 90.44 percent.

Table (1) Urban and Rural Population in Yesagyó Township (1973-2017)

Year	Urban		Rural		Total
	Person	Percent	Person	Percent	
1973	15,498	8.9	158,583	91.1	174,081
1983	19,461	9.2	191,755	90.8	211,216
1993	26,758	10.4	230,656	89.6	257,414
2003	39,437	12.4	279,609	87.6	319,046
2013	25,121	10.88	205,742	89.12	230,863
2014	23,329	10.8	192,023	89.2	215,352
2015	23,100	9.57	218,284	90.43	241,384
2016	23,101	9.51	219,560	90.49	242,611
2017	23,231	9.56	219,691	90.44	242,922

Source: Immigration and National Registration Department, Yesagyó.

MAP 1 LOCATION MAP OF YESAGYO TOWNSHIP

Source : One inch Topographic Map Sheets 84 K/11, 12, 15, 16, 84 L/9, 13, 84 O/1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7.

In Yesagyo Township, 26 village tracts are located on the islands at the confluence of Ayeyarwady and Chindwin rivers. In the rainy season, the water level of Ayeyarwady and Chindwin rivers reach their danger water level in Yesagyo Township. Therefore, the rural-urban migration occurs in Yesagyo Township.

General Land Use of Study Area

Agriculture is the leading occupation of Yesagyo Township. The main types of agricultural land in Yesagyo Township are 'Le' land, 'Ya' land, 'Kaing Kyun' land and 'Garden' land. In Yesagyo Township, the totals are of agricultural land was 113,301 acres in the year 2016-2017.

In Yesagyo Township, the area of 'Le' lands was 18,595 acres amounting to 16.41 percent of the total agricultural lands. Most of the 'Le' lands in Yesagyo Township were found in the western lowland regions at the foot of *Shinmataung* hill and in the eastern lowland regions at the confluence of the Ayeyarwady and Chindwin rivers. In 2016 'Ya' land area of Yesagyo Township was 66,516 acres amounting to 58.71 percent of the total agricultural lands. 'Ya' land is the largest area among the agricultural lands of Yesagyo Township.

'Kaing-Kyun' lands are mostly found on lands covered by alluviums and sediments which are formed during the rainy season and flood season. According to 2016-2017 statistical data, the area of 'Kaing Kyun' lands was 28,054 acres which amounted to 24.76 percent of the total agricultural land in Yesagyo Township. In 2016-2017, the area of garden land was 136 acres which amount to 0.12 percent of the total agricultural land in Yesagyo Township.

Water Resources and Irrigation

As Yesagyo Township lies in the Central Dry Zone Belt of Myanmar, the occurrence of rain is irregular and the amount of rainfall is also scanty. That is why in Yesagyo Township water required for the cultivation of crops is not sufficient. In 2016-2017 the total irrigated area within Yesagyo Township has seven river water pumping stations and five irrigation dams. Hence irrigation agriculture plays a major role for agriculture of Yesagyo Township. Water pumping stations are also mostly found along at the Ayeyarwady and Chindwin Rivers. According to the data 2016-17, out of the 81 village tracts and Yesagyo Town Proper, 70 village tracts can cultivated in the methods of irrigation. The remaining 12 village tracts are not cultivated in the methods of irrigation.

Variety of pulses cultivated in the study area

In 2016-2017, serially ordered pulses cultivated acres were chick pea 24,511 acres (32.35%), green gram 23,894 acres (31.54%), pigeon pea 7,225 acres (9.54%), cow pea 3,939 acres (5.20%), black gram 2,709 acres (3.58%), soya bean 2,063 acres (2.72%) and other pulses 11,417 acres (15.07%) as shown in figure (1). Yesagyo Township has a cultivated area of about 267,862 acres for all kinds of crops. Of these, the largest cultivated area for varieties of pulses is 75,758 acres Therefore, it has to be said that pulses are an important crop in the study area.

Figure (1) Cultivated Pulses in Yesagy Township. (2016-2017)

Spatial Analysis of Pulses concentration in study area

In analyzing the cultivation of pulses crops in Yesagy Township, it is found that chick pea, green gram, pigeon pea, cow pea, black gram, soya bean and other pulses are the dominant pulses. According to the statistical data of 2016-2017, the sown area of the seven dominant pulses was 75,758 acres and it amounted 30 percent of the total sown area of the crops within Yesagy Township. The level of concentration of pulses in the different village tracts was observed with the help of Location Quotient Method adopted by Dr. S. S. Bhatia. The formula of Location Quotient is as follows:

$$LQ = \frac{(X_i / X)}{(Y_i / Y)}$$

X_i = Area of particular crop in the Village Tract

X = Area of all crops in the Village Tract

Y_i = Area of particular crop in the Township

Y = Area of all crops in the Township

Within Yesagy Township, pulses were cultivated in Yesagy Town Proper and 81 village tracts. Table (2) shows the location quotient values in the study area in the year 2016-2017. The mean value of location quotient was 1.04 and standard deviation value was 1.01. According to positive skew the multiplied constant value change to 0.5. Based on these values three groups of concentration of pulses were classified as: Table (3) presents the spatial variation of pulses concentration in the study area.

1. High concentration of pulses (>1.55)
2. Medium concentration of pulses (Between 0.53 and 1.55)
3. Low concentration of pulses (< 0.53)

Table (2) Location Quotient of Pulses in Yesago Township.(2016-2017)

No	Town/ Village Tract	Area of Pulses (Acre)	Area of All Crops (Acre)	L.Q	No	Town/ Village Tract	Area of Pulses (Acre)	Area of All Crops (Acre)	L.Q
1	Yesago Town Proper	242	1,201	0.71	42	Nanoo	1,286	3,337	1.36
2	Gwegon	1,350	4,562	1.05	43	Yeshar	1,772	4,713	1.33
3	Byiba	1,221	5,246	0.82	44	Moekwe	756	4,036	0.66
4	Kanphyu	1,543	5,848	0.93	45	Kaing	993	2,925	1.20
5	Thitkyitaw	703	2,634	0.94	46	Ngatayaw	1,679	4,876	1.22
6	Watkataw	754	3,788	0.70	47	Myetaw	925	3,752	0.87
7	Payeintha	1,083	5,002	0.77	48	Bondawpyi	925	3,100	1.06
8	Lower Ma-U	779	1,857	1.48	49	Minywa	683	2,426	1.00
9	Middle Ma-U	479	3,373	0.50	50	Nayyin	850	2,797	1.07
10	Waya	901	4,989	0.64	51	Sindae	1,045	2,342	1.58
11	Myephyukyin	618	4,179	0.52	52	Kanthit	682	3,217	0.75
12	Kyatsukyin	324	1,435	0.80	53	Kyeekan	1,283	3,289	1.38
13	Ywarhtaung	364	3,714	0.35	54	Htando	650	1,865	1.23
14	Kokkosu	545	1,661	1.16	55	Kyaukka	477	2,215	0.76
15	Nipasayaw	657	1,353	1.72	56	Kaingmagyi	1,020	4,064	0.89
16	Tharzi	1,488	4,560	1.15	57	Thayetpinkan	635	1,939	1.16
17	Zeedaw	836	4,084	0.72	58	Pakhangyi	3,028	9,128	1.17
18	Taung-Oo	2,323	7,981	1.03	59	Pakhanng	2,948	7,159	1.46
19	Thanpyar Chaung	750	1,909	1.39	60	Kandaut	1,077	4,181	0.91
20	Sarlingone	397	2,267	0.62	61	Sinchaung	1,191	4,062	1.04
21	Ywarng	275	1,525	0.64	62	Zegone	804	4,344	0.65
22	Paungbedan	713	2,182	1.16	63	Mingan	875	2,869	1.08
23	Khwymyoke	361	1,344	0.95	64	Sithar	1,669	5,370	1.10
24	Thapyaypin	471	2,401	0.69	65	Htannggetaw	3,520	9,222	1.35
25	Mye phyu	541	3,896	0.49	66	Kyuywar	1,584	4,381	1.28
26	Zeegyun	31	100	1.10	67	Alegyaw	373	1,992	0.66
27	Nyaungtaw	563	3,421	0.58	68	Alethoung	539	2,552	0.75
28	Nyaungsauk	910	4,554	0.71	69	Yatthar	632	3,158	0.71
29	Myesoonaw	861	3,640	0.84	70	Zayama	658	2,350	0.99
30	Sinchayar	951	2,659	1.26	71	Kywedaunt	218	1,030	0.75
31	Thargaung	657	863	2.69	72	Layyapyi	437	1,331	1.16
32	Meelaungkyun	658	1,086	2.14	73	Ngarlan	239	3,725	0.23
33	Thamantapo	655	2,384	0.97	74	Maunkkalan	3,716	10,371	1.27
34	Sintkaing	1,152	2,164	1.88	75	Koyint	506	2,610	0.69
35	Kanbash	858	1,974	1.54	76	Hnaungba	586	3,373	0.61
36	Paygone	845	2,353	1.27	77	Ngamyargyi	226	410	1.95
37	Htansepin	704	1,460	1.71	78	Balaba	579	3,123	0.66
38	Ywarthit	946	2,880	1.16	79	Nweni	664	2,190	1.07
39	Kanoo	1,078	3,483	1.09	80	Aungpanchaung	343	1,388	0.87
40	Miphayar	821	3,754	0.77	81	Sinmaye	658	2,269	1.03
41	Warboe	1,255	3,252	1.36	82	Natngun	364	1,363	0.94
						Total			84.9
						Mean			1.04
						Standard Deviation			1.01

Source: Calculated by the Researcher.

Table (3) Spatial Variation of Pulses Concentration in Yesago Township (2016-2017)

Sr	Level of Concentration	Number of Town and Village Tracts
1	High (> 1.55)	7
2	Medium (between 0.53 and 1.55)	70
3	Low (< 0.53)	5

Source: Based on table (2).

Map (2) shows the concentration of pulses, the areas of high concentration of pulses was found in seven village tracts. Among these village tracts, Nipasataw Village Tract in western portion, Htansepin and Sintkaing village tracts in central portions, Sindae, Thargaung and Meelaungkyun village tracts in eastern portions and Ngamyargyi Village Tract in southern portion of the township have the level of high concentration of pulses because of fertile soils for cultivation of pulses.

The areas with medium concentration of pulses were found in Yesagyio Town Proper and 69 village tracts. That is why they amounted to 85 percent of the total pulses sown village tracts of Yesagyio Township. The village tracts with medium concentration of pulses were wide spread in all over the township. In these village tracts, pulses are cultivated by mix-cropping system by using rain water.

The areas with low concentration of pulses were found in five village tracts. Among these village tracts four village tracts are located in the northern and Ngarlan Village Tract is located in the southern part of the study area. They had the least concentration of pulses with 0.23 due to the river bank erosion of Ayeyarwady River.

Map (2) Concentration of Pulses in Yesagyio Township (2016-2017)

Source: Based on Table (3)

Analysis on trend of pulses cultivation and production in Yesagyo Township

To analyze the temporal changes of pulses cultivation in Yesagyo Township, pulses sown acreage and production during 15- year period from 2002-2003 to 2016-2017 are analysed by using regression line as a trend line. Temporal changes of crop cultivation and production in Yesagyo Township is examined by using regression analysis can shown below.

Trend of Pulses Sown Acreage in Yesagyo Township

According to table (4), during the 15- year period from 2002-03 to 2016-17, the average sown area of pulses in Yesagyo Township was 66,143 acres. There were 10 years with sown acreages of pulses more than the average sown area of pulses and 5 years with pulses sown area less than the average sown area of pulses. 2016-2017 was the year with the largest sown area of pulses amounting to 75,758 acres. According to the regression line in figure (2), it can be found that the increase in pulses sown acreage has occurred in the study area during the 15- year period from 2002-2003 to 2016-2017. Regarding pulses cultivation, the regression equation $y = 2061x + 49647$, correlation coefficient $R = 0.909$ and determinant $R^2 = 0.828$ indicate that yearly pulses cultivated acreage also increase over the years.

Table(4) Sown Acreages of Pulses in Yesagyo Township (2003-2017)

No	Year	Total Pulses Sown Acreage
1	2002-2003	50,154
2	2003-2004	51,233
3	2004-2005	51,377
4	2005-2006	53,495
5	2006-2007	57,083
6	2007-2008	69,056
7	2008-2009	70,368
8	2009-2010	71,359
9	2010-2011	71,750
10	2011-2012	72,737
11	2012-2013	73,845
12	2013-2014	75,900
13	2014-2015	74,406
14	2015-2016	73,619
15	2016-2017	75,758
	Total	992,140
	Average	66,143

Source: Department of Agricultural Land Management and Statistic, Yesagyo.

Trend of Pulses Production in Yesagyo Township

During the 15- year period, the average matured acreage of pulses was 66,143 acres and the average yield per acre of pulses was 15.2 baskets. During the period the average production of pulses was totaled 1,028,573 baskets. According to table(5), there was eight years with production of pulses more than the average production of pulses and seven years with the production of pulses less than the average production of pulses. According to the regression line in figure (3), it can be found that the increase in pulses production has occurred in the study area during the 15- year period from 2002-2003 to 2016-2017. According to the result, the regression equation $y = 76257x + 41851$, correlation coefficient $R = 0.9685$ and determinant

$R^2 = 0.938$ indicate that yearly pulses produced basket also increase over the years. The reason is possible pulses are usually cultivated double and mixed in year but systematic uses of fertilizers and pesticides are still needed. So, irrigation is necessary to cultivate farmer's favorite pulses to get high yield and to get maximum pulses production.

Table(5) Production of Pulses in Yesagy Township (2003-2017)

No	Year	Production Basket
1	2002-2003	508356
2	2003-2004	524657
3	2004-2005	587863
4	2005-2006	629366
5	2006-2007	700184
6	2007-2008	916936
7	2008-2009	1026442
8	2009-2010	1150132
9	2010-2011	1222835
10	2011-2012	1287893
11	2012-2013	1310122
12	2013-2014	1373823
13	2014-2015	1371066
14	2015-2016	1335964
15	2016-2017	1482953
	Total	15428592
	Average	1,028,573

Source: Department of Agricultural Land Management and Statistic, Yesagy.

Findings Result and Suggestion

In Yesagy Township there is a total agricultural land (sown acreage) of 113,404 acres of which 67 percent is used as cultivated land of pulses. Among the physical bases, terrain and soils are the most distinctive bases for pulses cultivation in the study area. Along the eastern border of the township, it can be found that Ayeyarwady and Chindwin rivers flow from north to south. So, Ayeyarwady and Chindwin river valleys are suitable for varieties of pulses cultivation. Zeekyun Village Tract is cultivated only one pigeon pea because this village tract is situated in the western bank of Chindwin River near Yesagy Town Proper due to the river bank erosion of Chindwin River.

According to table (6), shows comparative study of pulses concentration in the study area. Green gram plays an important role in the economy of Yesagy Township. Within Yesagy Township, green gram was cultivated in Yesagy Town Proper and 80 village tracts. Chick pea and green gram are the most important pulses in Yesagy Township. Chick pea and green gram are the largest sown areas of the township. That is why the pulses are cultivated in the plain area where cultivable lands with fertile soils due to the deposition of Ayeyarwady and Chindwin rivers are available.

In Yesagy Township, as pulses sown acreage differs in each village tract and it is related with the relief, soil type and rainfall condition, the temporal changes within the village tract can be seen also.

Table (6) Comparative Study of Pulses Concentration in the Study Area (2016-2017).

Sr No	Kind of Pulses	Number of Town and Village Tracts with the Level of Concentration		
		High	Medium	Low
1	Chick Pea	17	39	20
2	Green Gram	23	29	29
3	Pigeon Pea	7	34	5
4	Cow Pea	7	49	2
5	Black Gram	7	27	4
6	Soya Bean	4	33	1
7	Other Pulses	11	41	8

Source: Compiled by the Researcher.

After 2005-2006, pulses was became the most popular crop for export. The pulses sown acreage had increased year after year in the study area. Because of the farmers use modern ploughing machines extensively in pulses cultivation, the yield per acre of pulses increased year after year. In the western portions, these village tracts are situated in the foothills of *Shinmataung, Taung- Oo Taung and Kyaukhtat Taung*, the agriculture is not favourable due to rugged topography and insufficient of water. If supplying of irrigation water is supported and the above mentioned necessities are fulfilled, the living standard and social status of the local people of study area will become higher and the township will certainly develop in all aspects in the near future.

In the 70 village tracts and Yesagyio Town Proper in Yesagyio Township, pulses can be cultivated by the irrigation method. By using these pump sets; pulses are being cultivated by irrigation. However, it is found that the supply of irrigation water is inadequate due to shortage of electricity that runs motors of pump sets. For that, electricity should be supplied at a cheap rate whenever necessary. Depending upon availability of water supply of irrigation, pulses are usually cultivated double and mixed in year but systematic uses of fertilizers and pesticides are still needed. Irrigation is necessary to cultivate farmer's favorite pulses to get high yield and to get maximum pulses production.

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၁။ မိုးလေဝသနှင့် ဇလဗေဒဦးစီးဌာန - အပူချိန်နှင့် မိုးရေချိန်စာရင်းများ(၁၉၈၈-၂၀၁၇)။ ရေစကြို မြို့နယ်
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 ၃။ ကြေးတိုင် နှင့် မြေစာရင်းဦးစီးဌာန - မြေအသုံးချမှုဖော်ပြသောစာရင်းများ (၂၀၁၆-၂၀၁၇)။